

Paper 21

EFFECTS OF MUSIC ON COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF TEENAGERS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we describe the effects of music on cognitive development of teenagers. **Music is a form of art; an expression of emotions through harmonic frequencies.** Most music includes people singing with their voices or playing musical instruments, such as the piano, guitar, drums or violin. Music can be found in every culture all around the world. Music has become such a big part of our lives, that researchers can't help but want to study how music affects people, especially teenagers. Music affects various aspects of **cognitive development such as perception, memory, language skills, information processing, intelligence, reasoning and memory** etc. The purpose of this conceptual paper is to music involvement in teenagers lives to help develop memory, perception, language, vocabulary, spoken skills and reading skills. Music can helpful tool to enrich teenager's cognitive development. The effects of music on cognitive development of teenagers is elaborated with its aim, underlying principles and concepts, particular contextual features or challenging issues that have had to be addressed in detail.

Keywords : Music, Cognitive, Development, Teenagers, Skills.

1. Introduction

Music is a form of art; an expression of emotions through harmonic frequencies. Most music includes people singing with their voices or playing musical instruments, such as the piano, guitar, drums or violin. Music can be found in every culture all around the world. Music has become such a big part of our lives, that researchers can't help but want to study how music affects people, especially teenagers. Some researchers are interested in documenting effects that listening to music may have on teenager's cognitive development.

Our investigation of the literature on the effects of music in a teenagers life, inspired us to create a resource for families who wish to promote and support their adolescence interest in the arts, specifically music. The form of this resource was a print booklet that parents could use as a guide to local music options. We also gathered information through word of mouth, asking for information from the music department, and looking on the internet for other existing musical programs. We compiled all of the information and put them into five

categories: opportunities to observe music, ways to learn about music, informal ways to actively participate in music, ways to actively participate in a group setting, and places to get instruction. We provided a list of programs to get involved with, as well as a list of private instructors at the very end of the music guide. It emphasizes the importance of music involvement in teenager's lives to help develop memory, perception, language, vocabulary, spoken skills, and reading skills. We sought to educate and inform parents of the many ways that music can be a helpful tool to enrich teenager's cognitive development.

There is a need to study and test teenager's interest in music and its influences on the outcomes of teenager's academic performance. It would be intriguing if there could be an online network that would be setup for musicians and music organizations to collaborate and put themselves out there for the community, and to expand the music guide, adding to its resources. Although our guide does have some limitations, it is our hope that we educate parents and the community on the importance of music in teenager's lives.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Many parents, teachers, scholars, and businesses are interested in learning more about the influence of music on the cognitive development of teenager's. Teenagers could potentially be influenced by music in several ways. Some researchers investigate whether and how teenager's benefit from listening to music. Others focus on how formal music training impacts various aspects of cognitive development such as perception, memory, and language skills. Examination of the findings from each of these avenues of research can support teenager's learning.

Some researchers are interested in documenting effects that listening to music may have on teenager's cognitive development. One line of work in this area focuses on what teenager's learn about music itself by listening to music. Another line of work investigates how listening to particular forms of music may impact cognitive development outside of the musical domain. Explorations of the influence of experience on teenager's ability to match auditory and visual stimuli within the domain of music are an example of the first research direction.

While instrument identification does not have any implications outside of a musical domain, it leads to question whether listening to music has an effect on other areas of cognitive development outside of music. **Rauscher and Shaw (1993)** which found that **college students** who listened to Mozart's sonata in D major prior to taking a standard test of abstract spatial reasoning scored higher on tests of spatial intelligence than college students who listened to either some relaxing music or no music at all.

In contrast to the disputed nature of the **Mozart Effect**, research clearly reveals that music training has an influence on a variety of aspects of cognitive development in adolescence. There are many different types of musical skills a person learns when he/she is involved in musical training. For example, a musician needs to know how to physically play and work his/her instrument, or how to make vocal sounds the correct way. A musician also needs to know how to read music. In order to read music, a musician needs to know how to read different intervals between different notes on a staff and translate them to his/her instrument. The faster a person can read and interpret notes on a staff, the faster he/she can play his/her

instrument. Sight-reading is a skill that has to be practiced repeatedly in order to do it successfully.

The **cognitive processes of reading music also manufactures rhythm and structure**. In order to read music successfully, a musician needs to read the correct rhythms if the music is to be performed correctly. A musician also needs to pay attention to the meter, the tempo, the bar lines, and the phrases, which points to the overall structure of the music. Developing expertise in each of these areas enables a musician to put together a performance that is pleasing to not only the musician, but also to an audience. Music instruction is critical in helping musicians to develop these skills. An interesting question in the psychological literature is whether and how this type of training also impacts development more generally, such as within the areas of brain development perception, language, and memory.

Anvari et al. (2002) found that music skills were correlated with phonological awareness and early reading skills. The basic auditory skills for music perception were similar to early reading skills which shared some of the same auditory mechanisms that predicted reading ability.

Enhanced listening skills help develop linguistic organization. In a study **Milovanov, Tervaniemi, and Gustafsson (2004, as cited in Milovanov, Tervaniemi, Takio, & Hämäläinen, 2007)** suggest that there is a connection between music and language skill (Milovanov, Tervaniemi, Takio, & Hämäläinen, 2007). This led Milovanov, Tervaniemi, Takio, & Hämäläinen (2007) to believe that musical expertise might possibly affect the dominance of one side of the brain in controlling the musical and linguistic processing in the brain.

Southgate and Roscigno (2009) examined the relationship between music training and academic achievement among adolescents 13-17 years old. In order to measure this, they looked at music participation in three separate contexts: in school, outside of school, and parent involvement in the form of concert attendance. Looking at nationally representative data resources, the researchers found that music involvement had a positive association with grades and math and reading scores. What was concluded was that music is meaningful not as predictor of achievement but as a medium to support teenager's achievement.

3. Statement Of Problem

The aim of the study was to the Effects Of Music On Cognitive Development Of Teenagers.

Objectives

To assess the Effects Of Music On Cognitive Development Of Teenagers.

Operational definition

Music is a form of art; an expression of emotions through harmonic frequencies.

Cognitive development is a complex thinking of adolescence and they have ability to deal with formal logical operations such as perception, memory, language skills, information processing, intelligence, reasoning and memory , abstract thinking and aware of thought process etc.

4. Scope of the study

- **The relationship between music and the frontal lobes found that in general,** music increased activity within the left frontal lobes, which is associated with

happiness . This may in turn explain why music creates an environment with less tension. "Music in the classroom reduces stress, increases productivity, regulates energy, and creates a relaxed, supportive learning environment" (Davies, 2000, pg. 150). Along with this, 'there is clear evidence that music affects brain waves and physiological states," says Yoon. The influence of music on the stress levels of adult hospital patients. One group of anesthetized surgery patients listened to music on headphones while another group did not. The 'music' group had lower stress levels in the blood" (2000, pg. 24). This research may transfer to children and prove that children with anxiety may lower their stress levels when music is included daily in the learning process.

➤ **A connection between music and math** was also found during a **neurological research** study. It was documented that " higher brain functions of abstract reasoning as well as spatial and temporal conceptualization are enhanced by music activities. Activities with music can generate the neural connections necessary for using important math skills" (Church, 2000/2001 , p.50). Church also points out that "music is considered a right-brain activity. while math is a left-brain activity. When combined, the whole adolescent is engaged not only in the realm of thinking. but in all the other domains of social-emotional, creative and physical development" (2000/2001 , p.50).

➤ **Cognitive Growth Of Teenagers**

- a) Each Teenager's moves ahead at their own rate in their ability to think in more complex ways.
- b) Each Teenager's develops their own view of the world.
- c) Some Teenager's may be able to use logical operations in schoolwork long before they can use them for personal problems.
- d) When emotional issues come up, they can cause problems with a Teenager's ability to think in complex ways.
- e) The ability to consider possibilities and facts may affect decision-making. This can happen in either positive or negative ways.

➤ Using **music in the classroom for various reasons**, such as; decoding skills (because music and reading use sounds and symbols), listening skills (they both require imagination), rhythm skills, communication skills (verbal and written responses), vocabulary development (new words and meanings often encountered), expressive ability, memorization, and motor development through playing instruments and creative movement . Students can " rewrite the lyrics to familiar songs. Younger grades can work on phonological awareness by substituting individual rhyming words".

5. Limitations

The limitations of the study is as society and networking continues to progress, it would be interesting to see how this guide can further expand its' reach to other spheres like the Internet. It would be fascinating if there could be an online network that would be setup for musicians and music organizations to collaborate and put themselves out there for the community, and to expand the music guide, adding to its resources.

6. Conclusion

Music aptitude is associated with linguistic abilities, including phonological processing, facility with acquiring a second language, and in some instances, reading, whereas the notion of a special link between natural musical and mathematical abilities has virtually no empirical support. Moreover, many of the positive findings may be attributable to a more general association between music aptitude and cognitive functioning.

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The research emphasizes the importance of music involvement in teenager's lives to help develop memory, perception, language, vocabulary, spoken skills, and reading skills. We sought to educate teenager's of the many ways that music can be a helpful tool to enrich their cognitive development. In addition, we created a resource for parents to help them easily find local musical opportunities with which to get their teenager's involved. These resources gives teenager's an opportunity to observe music, ways to learn about music, informal ways to actively participate in music, ways to actively participate in a group setting, and places to get instruction.

7. References

1. Drake, C., & Palmer, C. (2000). Skill acquisition in music performance: Relations between planning and temporal control. *Cognition*, 74(1), 1-32. doi:10.1016/S0010-0277(99)00061-X.
2. Forgeard, M. (2008). Practicing a musical instrument in childhood is associated with enhanced verbal ability and nonverbal reasoning.
3. Franklin M., Moore, K., Yip, C., Jonides, J., Rattray, K., & Moher, J. (2008). The effects of musical training on verbal memory. *Psychology of Music*, 36(3), 353-365. doi:10.1177/0305735607086044.
4. Gromko, J. (2005). The effect of music instruction on phonemic awareness in beginning readers. *Journal of Research in Music Education*, 53(3), 199-209. doi:10.2307/3598679.
5. Ho, Y., Cheung, M., & Chan, A. (2003). Music training improves verbal but not visual memory: Cross-sectional and longitudinal explorations in children. *Neuropsychology*, 17(3), 439- 450. doi:10.1037/0894-4105.17.3.439.
6. Hyde, K., Lerch, J., Norton, A., Winner, E., Schlaug, G., Evans, A., et al. (2009). Musical training shapes structural brain development. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 29(10), 3019- 3025. doi:10.1523/JNEUROSCI.5118-08.2009.
7. Schellenberg, E. G. (2004). Music lessons enhance IQ. *Psychological Science*, 15, 11 - 514.
8. We inberger, N. M. (1998, November). The music in our minds. *Educational Leadership*, 56(3), 36-40.